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**THE IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STAFF QUALIFICATION ON THE QUALITY OF GRADUATE
TEACHER PREPARATION IN TANZANIA HIGHER EDUCATION**

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QUALITY OF GRADUATE TEACHER PREPARATION IN TANZANIA
HIGHER EDUCATION**

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Submitted: September 12, 2019

Abstract

This paper assesses the influence of academic staff qualification on the graduate teacher preparation in Tanzania. A total of 44 informants from four universities were involved in the study. The study was underpinned by qualitative research, using multiple case study design. Interviews and document analyses were used to obtain data. The findings indicated that there is inadequate number of senior academic staff in all the studied universities. It was also revealed that some departments had neither a professor nor senior lecturer specialized in teacher education. The findings further indicate that there is a mismatch between number of student-teachers enrolled in education programme and that of the academic staff available in all studied universities. Thus, based on the findings, it is logically to argue that inadequate academic staff in universities in Tanzania where graduate teachers are prepared has an implication on their learning outcome.

Keywords: Universities, Academic Qualification, Teacher preparation

1. Introduction

Ever since 2005, the Government of Tanzania (GOT) has been financing teacher education by providing loans to student-teachers enrolled in teacher education programmes in both public and private universities using the public/private model of financing teacher education (Mgaiwa & Poncian, 2016; MoEVT, 2014). The same year 2005, the Tanzania Commission for Universities (TCU) was established to replace the Higher Education Accreditation Council (HEAC) as a statutory body to oversee and control the quality of higher education in the country. Areas of considerations include: enrolment, infrastructures and academic staff. In other words, since 2005 universities have been playing the central role in the preparation of graduate teachers besides other none teacher education instructional fields. As a result, universities are currently enrolling a relatively high number of student teachers in education programmes than other degree

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programmes (Mgaiwa, 2018; Mgaiwa & Poncian, 2016;TCU, 2014) .These rapid increase in the enrolment raises concern about the extent to which Tanzanian universities have an adequate number of qualified academic staff as compared to attend to increased needs of the student-teachers.

2. Literature review

2.1 Academic and Professional Qualification of Academic Staff.

The academic and professional qualifications of university academics have been a major concern in the 21st century worldwide; and Tanzania in particular. Quality of academic staff is key aspect in quality teaching and learning process in higher learning institutions. All over the world, academic staff members have been playing a great role in teaching, research and consultancy (Fussy, 2018; Metcalf, Rolfe, Stevens & Weale, 2015; Enders, 2001). The relevant qualifications of the academic staff are essential in facilitating learning and ensuring quality of education provided (Houston, Meyer & Paewai, 2006).

It is therefore plausible to assert that effective teacher preparation in universities needs to provide adequate academic content knowledge and sound professional skills. In deed adequate content knowledge and sound professional skills in universities depends on the calibre of teaching staff faculty hold. A lecturer (PhD) realise competence to deliver satisfactory research and teaching; while a senior lecturer need knowledge and skills to deliver more advanced satisfactory research and teaching. A professor needs to offer plausible knowledge and skills with high level of creativity and productivity in teaching, research and consultancy as well as leadership in all academic and professional positions. He/she is an excellent researcher with enough experience and well known in his/her area/discipline (Teferra & Altbach, 2004; Enders, 2001). Thus, universities need to have a balanced number of professors, senior lecturers, lecturers proportional to the enrolment rate of student teachers to create conducive environment for quality learning (Altbach, Reisberg, & Rumbley, 2009; Altbach & Knight, 2007).

However, the available evidence show that there are a few academic staff who have the desirable qualifications for preparing graduate teachers in universities (Anney, 2014; Peter, 2014; Areaya, 2010). This, in turn, has led to a widespread questioning of the quality of outputs who have failed

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to provide quality instruction in the classroom (Mgaiwa, 2018; Mgaiwa & Poncian, 2016; Kitta & Fussy, 2013; Mulokozi, 2012). Research evidence indicates a paucity of research based information on whether the current increase in enrolment of student-teachers matched the number of available academic staff (Mgaiwa & Ishengoma, 2017; Ishengoma, 2007). In this regard, the interest of this article was to answer two major research questions: What is the status of academic staff qualification in school/faculty of education in selected universities? And What are the implications of the current status of academic staff qualification in school/faculty of education in selected universities in the preparation of graduate teachers?

3. Conceptual Framework

The following conceptual has been developed from literatures and empirical studies reviewed:

Figure 1.1 Conceptual framework of the study

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The conceptual framework illustrates the availability of adequate academic staff with required academic and professional qualifications and its implication in graduate teacher preparation. Context is social economic and environment in which university operate (TCU; university qualification framework) which is responsible for issuing guidelines of academic and professional qualification for academic staff in universities. Currently TCU sets requirements and guidelines regarding academic and professional qualification for academic staff in universities which are not effectively charted. Yet the conceptual framework suggest that for quality graduate teachers preparation universities need health input that are adequate academic staff with required academic and professional qualification who will influence quality teaching and learning through their commitment in teaching, research and consultation of students teachers as well as mentorship of junior staff members.

4. Methodology

This study used qualitative approach with multiple case study design. Four universities were sampled for the study (two public and two private); namely University of Dar es salaam (UDSM), University of Dodoma (UDOM), Mwenge Catholic University (MWECAU) and Morogoro Muslim University (MMU). The selection of these universities was based on the availability of teacher education programmes hence having adequate number of student teachers apart from researcher's acquisition of rich in teacher preparation for both science and arts subjects.

Moreover, UDSM and UDOM are the largest public universities with high enrolment of student-teachers in education programmes. MWECAU and MUM are private universities with high enrolment of student-teachers in education programmes (science and arts). A total of 44 participants were engaged in the study. They included particularly 4 Deputy Vice Chancellors (DVCs), 4 Deans, 34 Head of Departments (HoD) from (education, physics, biology, chemistry,

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history and geography), 1 Professor and 1 Senior Lecturer. All participants were purposively selected based on their strategic positions in teacher preparation.

Data were collected through semi-structured interview and documentary analysis. Semi-structured interviews allowed collection of vast information in a natural setting, with why and how questions (Cohen, 2007). With the consent of the study's participants, interviewees' responses were recorded by a voice recorder and short notes were taken in to notebooks which were then transcribed verbatim before subjected to formal analysis and discussion. Documentary analysis was used to validate findings from the interviews to achieve triangulation of data, minimizing bias and ensuring trustworthiness of the study's findings. The documents analysed were universities' prospectus, academic staff qualification manuals, and TCU guidelines.

Data were analysed through Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis, based on six major stages: familiarisation with data by reading and re-reading, generating initial codes, searching for the themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes and report writing (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Moreover, the researcher used qualitative data analysis software Nvivo 10 and later Nvivo 11 to facilitate the analysis and interpretation process. Nvivo is the most powerful computer program in qualitative studies for it allows organisation and management of data. It facilitated the coding process, with well arrangement of memo, annotations and links. Then it also facilitated the running of complex queries, and framework matrix which helped the researcher to explore patterns and themes.

5. Findings and Discussion

The findings were organised in two subsections: professional qualifications of academic staff and implications on preparing graduate teachers.

5.1 Academic and professional qualifications of academic staff

Regarding qualifications of academic staff in sampled universities, the findings indicated that most universities under review did not have adequate number of professors and senior lecturers to meet the requirements as per enrolment rate of student teachers as well as TCU guideline.

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Moreover, the findings show that one university had inadequate academic staff in general. The situation is summarized in tabular form as per tables 1(a,b) herein.

Table 1(a): Number of Academic Staff in school/college/faculty/department of education

Universities	Professors	Senior Lecturers	Lecturers	Assistant Lecturers	Tutorial Assistants
UN A	9	12	34	16	6
UN B	1	4	24	77	6
UN C	1	2	9	9	1
UN D	0	0	2	4	1

Source: Field Data 2017/2018

Table 1(b): Number of Academic Staff in department of physics, chemistry, biology, geography and history)

		Physics	Chemistry	Biology	Geography	History
UN A	Professors	03	05	02	04	02
	Senior Lecturers	06	07	03	06	04
	Lecturers	02	08	08	14	06
	Assistant Lecturers	04	07	01	20	06
	Tutorial Assistants	-	01	-	05	01
	Total		15	28	15	45
UN B	Professor	-	02	01	02	01
	Senior Lecturer	-	05	08	04	01
	Lecturer	10	06	12	14	02
	Assistant lecturer	11	10	22	18	12
	Tutorial assistant	4	01	05	16	01
	Total		25	24	48	40
UN C	Prof	-	-	-	-	-
	Senior Lecturer	-	01	01	-	-
	Lecturer	-	02	03	-	-
	Assistant lecturer	11	02	08	06	03
	Tutorial assistant	-	-	-	01	02
	Total		11	05	12	07
UN D	Prof	-	-	-	-	-
	Senior Lecturer	-	-	-	-	-

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Lecturer	-	01	-	01	-
Assistant lecturer	-	01	4	03	-
Tutorial assistant	02	01	-	-	02
Total	02	03	5	04	02

Source: Field Data 2017/2018

Generally data from tables 1a and 1b indicated that academic staff in the departments is inadequate when compared to number of students enrolled. Data from documentary reviews indicated that student teachers from universities studied were about 4915 in UN A, 7226 in UN B, 3788 in UN C and 1586 in UN D. Comparatively, the available number of academic staff and number of student teachers enrolled in education programme suggests that academic staffs in all sampled universities were inadequate. The critical shortage of academic staff was noted among the professors and senior lecturers across the disciplines, because the majority were lecturers and assistant lecturers. Similarly, in the departments, senior lecturers in the university 'A' are not adequate to provide desirable output to meet the needs of available student teachers admitted and other academic activities in the particular department. In university 'A', the department with the highest number of senior lecturers was Chemistry (7) followed by Geography (6) and Physics (6).

Data in Table (b) show that at University 'A' there is high shortage of professors followed by senior lecturers and lecturers. For example, the findings unveiled that in University A, 7 out of 9 professors (i.e. over two-third were retired due to old age and were working on contractual basis or part times teaching) which could not be renewed anymore, leaving a large manpower gap within the institution. It was also revealed that few available professors and senior lecturers were appointed to hold other responsibilities out of academic context a situation which also increased the deficit. In this regard, one respondent from university A, said:

Academic staff has been in a potential shortfall in the university as a system. Within a short while some of the employees left for greener pastures elsewhere. Others retire and die out leaving gaps in the institution. The Government has banned employment of academic staff for a long time. Almost four years an elapsed and university stopped employing new staff for lack of government approval. Also there are numerous senior academic staffs

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(professors and senior lecturers whose contracts are no longer being renewed. This group comprise almost one-third of that cadre many do not want to be engaged as part timers as such arrangement is demeaning to them **(Interview-SL from UN A)**).

Another academic staff provided his views on the subject of shortage of senior academic staff as follows

We have number of senior academic staffs who have been appointed to hold various positions out of academic institutions. Actually it's an achievement to them but to university it's a loss. This is because they left big gaps specifically in the school of education. There are also people who retire every year. The other reason, for shortage of academic staff is 'study leave' which takes them almost four years and above away from work stations and it's a continuous process **(interview-DVCA; UN A)**.

In university B, the findings from the college of education show that there is 1 Prof, 3 SLs 24 Ls 77 ALs and 6 tutorial assistants. The findings indicate high inadequate number of professors and senior lecturers in college of education more than in academic content departments (physics, chemistry, biology, geography and history); which is likely to affect negatively the coverage of pedagogical knowledge of teacher prepared. During interview it was stressed that:

Shortage of senior academic staff is a problem. As you can see; senior lecturer and professor are only 4. So far quality teacher preparation with huge number of junior academic staff is not promising. So the only solution is to encourage available junior academic staff to pursue further studies; including motivating them to perform more research and publish for them to be promoted to senior ranks. However, conducting research and publications has been a problem to many lecturers. I don't know why? But I think they are overloaded with teaching and learning activities and other responsibilities within the college **(Interview- Deans UN B)**.

Another respondent point out that:

Collage of education is crowded with assistant lecturers and lecturers. Senior academic staffs (professor and senior lectures) are very few they are less than five. This is not how it supposed to be if quality teacher preparation were to be realised. But the situation is associated by top down kind of management. So we have nothing to do about that **(Interview- TPC UN B)**.

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In university C, the findings revealed that Faculty of Education has 1 professor and 2 senior lecturers. However, in the academic subject departments' findings revealed that in all 5 departments there were no professors. In the department of Chemistry and Biology there is one senior lecture each, with two and three lecturer respectively. In the department of physics, geography and history, Assistant lecturers override other staff; followed by tutorial Assistants.

During the interview it was revealed that the head of three departments/unit (physics, history and geography) are assistant lecturers a practice that was contrary to provisions of the universities act which demand such position to be occupied by senior faculty members. This implies that in those department/unity no senior lecturer at all. When data from documentary analysis were cross checked with data from interview the findings confirms excessive shortage of senior academic staff in academic subjects.

In University 'D', the findings revealed that in the department of Education, there were 2 lecturers and 4 assistant lecturers. Moreover there was neither a professor nor senior lecturer. With regards to academic subject; findings revealed that in all departments (physics, chemistry, biology, history and geography) there were neither professors nor senior lecturers. In the departments of physics, biology, and history there is not even a lecturer. Again in the Department of Physics and History there was no assistance lecturer. One respondent stressed that:

Currently we are facing excessive shortage of lecturers' specifically senior ranks. The situation is influenced by number of factors....like currently were university is facing financial problem more than before. However we are struggling to overcome the challenge as much as we can. **(Interview-Dean-UN D)**.

However the researcher wanted to know the reasons behind the excessive shortage of not only senior rank but also in other junior rank; the findings revealed that few junior academic staff was at study leave inside and outside the country. A respondent said that:

Frankly speaking in this university we have a shortage of academic staff however we have number of academic staff who are on study leave. As you know post graduate studies take long compared to other studies **(Interviews-DVC- UN D)**.

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The findings suggest that university 'D' is facing acute shortage of academic staff in general. When data from interviews were cross checked with data from documentary analysis the findings revealed confirm excessive inadequate teaching staff in both department of education and academic subject department. However analysis of TCU document revealed that for programme to have less than 5 PhD holders and less than 5 Masters holders is not acceptable.

Generally, the findings revealed that in all visited universities there are inadequately staffed especially in the ranks of professors and senior lecturers. These findings imply that junior academics such as lecturers and assistant lecturers are heavily relied upon to facilitate teaching and learning as well as other managerial positions. The finding collaborate with early study conducted in Ethiopia, Zimbabwe and Kenya that universities are had inadequate number of senior academic staff hence universities are staffed with assistance lecturers and tutorial assistance (Garwe, 2015; Gudo, Olel, & Oanda, 2011; Areaya, 2010).

Arguably inadequate number of professors and senior lecturers across teachers' preparation disciplines in all surveyed universities, is the common practice in mostly African universities which has implication on provision of quality education (Mgaiwa & Ishengoma, 2017; Kitta & Fussy, 2013;. This is due to the fact that senior lecturers are vibrant aspect in any higher learning institution whereby their roles are not only in teaching students' teachers but also in mentorship of junior academic staff, as well as assuring quality learning is provided to enhance quality product (Mushemeza, 2016; Enders, 2001).

Indeed senior academic staff (professor and senior lecturers) apart from providing more than average teaching activities they are capable in evidencing consultancy, mentoring junior academic staff as well as leadership in high academic and professional positions for benefit of the society (Altbach & Knight, 2007). Therefore once higher learning institution had acute shortage of high rank position in academic and professional programme the quality of product anticipated remain questionable. In the same lines of argument Mgaiwa & Ishengoma, (2017) gratified that when university have academic staff with lower ranks, quality assurance of the programme is questionable. This implies that academic staff with lower ranks alone are not in a position to provide quality learning.

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On the contrary, it was implausible to find out that in most cases UN B C and D some of managerial position (head of departments) in teacher preparation is led by junior academic staff. The findings implies that in those departments where heads are junior staff there is missing of incredible consultancy as well as leadership of particular department might not be encouraging due to insufficiency of academic maturity and experience of the head of department.

Similar findings were reported from the study that examined African higher education: Challenges for the 21st century (Teferra & Altbach, 2004). The study found shortage of senior academic staff in higher learning institution that led to junior staff to head the managerial position while they are having little or no working experience at all. In this regards the quality of education provided teacher is at risk due to lack of required experience and academic maturity among junior academic staff. Thus, for a university to achieve its mission and vision it needs adequate number of high ranked academic staff for managerial and mentorship of not only students but also junior staff (UNESCO, 2015; UNESCO, 2009; Teferra & Altbach, 2004).

In addition findings from UN D suggest that there is inadequate number of academic staff in general in both teacher education and academic subjects department. Critical analysis indicated that in teacher education programme academic staffs holding PhDs are less than five the situation which is unacceptable according to TCU quality assurance guidelines. Acceptable PhDs academic staff per programme is 5 in numbers (TCU,2014). The findings suggest that there is extreme inadequate number of academic staff professor and senior lecturers particularly in one of the sampled private universities when compared to public universities.

Plethora of early study conducted in African private universities reported similar findings that private universities overloaded by academic staff with low ranks that are assistance lecturer and tutorial assistant (Mgaiwa & Ishengoma, 2017; Nuru, 2017; Garwe, 2015; Peter, 2014; Mwebi & Simatwa, 2013; Mugabi, 2012). In the same line, Mwebi & Simatwa (2013) found that 68% of teaching staff in private universities have masters and bachelor degrees. In a similar disposition the study by Peter (2010) found that most academic staff had inadequate academic qualifications which reduced the ability of these private universities to meet the core functions of a university to provide quality teaching. However in university context tutorial assistance and assistant lecturer are not regarded as a teaching force rather are training post in which they are

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supposed to pursue their respective degree relative in a short time (TCU, 2014; Komba, et al 2013). The findings suggest that the quality of learning provided in such situations is uncertain. In addition the findings suggest that in wide range administrative and managerial positions like heads of departments are handled by junior academic staff. For private universities the situation is contributed by the fact that universities are facing critical financial limitation.

Several studies have also shown that required qualification of academic staff in private universities has been a major challenge with no or little solution (Mgaiwa & Ishengoma, 2017; Jin & Jiang, 2016; Hornsby & Oman, 2014; Peter, 2010; Munene, 2009; UNESCO, 2009; Ishengoma, 2007). In resolving the matter, private universities depend on part-time academic staff from public universities (Metcalf, Rolfe, Stevens & Weale, 2015) which when they usually allowed to stay few days in the host institution and tend to rush in their teaching to minimise cost.

5.2 Implications in preparing graduate teachers

The study revealed that due to the shortage of qualified professional academic staff, most of studied universities had high academic staff-student teacher ratio. For example, in university ‘D’ ratio was 1:226, followed by university C 1:172 and university A with ratio of 1:74. Only one university had a ratio of 1:64 which was still high. During analysis of the TCU document findings revealed that ideal staff student ratio is 1:40 for arts social science and humanities while science and technology is 1:20, more than that is not acceptable. See Table 2.

Table: 2 Student-teachers against Academic staff ratio in School/College/Faculty/of Education

Universities	Academic Staff	Student Teachers	Ratio
UN A	64	4915	1:74
UN B	112	7226	1:64

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UN C	22	3788	1:172
UN D	7	1586	1:226

Sources: Field Data 2017/2018

From the data in the Table 2 one can draw a conclusion that all visited universities had academic staff-student teachers ratio which is relatively high as it exceeded ideal ratio of 1:40 for arts, social science and humanities; 1:20 for science subjects as stipulated by TCU documents. In this regard, one of the academic staff at UN B said:

The ratio of staff: students in this university are relatively high compared to the number of academic staff available. This problem originated from top authorities...despite of enrolling a moderate number of students who could match with the number of academic staff employed, they are enrolling high number of students to satisfy politician's ego without considering desired faculty needed (**Interview-TPC;UN B**).

Similar views were provided by another academic staff from UN A who said:

We have a very big number of students in this university. The enrolment is relatively high compared to number of academic staff available. Indeed it is very challenging to meet students' academic needs when it comes to classroom teaching and running seminar and tutorials (**Interview-HoD; UN A**).

Above citation suggest that the staff student ratio is high compared to what is articulated in the TCU documents. The findings implies that available academic staff have heavy teaching workload as a result of academic staff shortage while the number of students admitted is big which is experienced with sampled universities. The analysis of national and institutional policy documents indicated the shortage of academic staff within universities was due to the 1990s' employment freeze, retirement, massification as well as relocation to newly openly universities and non-academic position (TCU 2014; URT 2014). As such, given their shortage in supply, available academic staffs were over-utilized.

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The plethora of literature revealed that universities are facing heavy teaching workloads due to massification while number of qualified and experience academic staff is inadequate in most African countries (Jin & Jiang, 2016; Hornsby & Oman, 2014; TCU, 2014; Woods, 2008; Ladson-billings, 2000). Massification is more antagonistic in developing countries due to limited access to teaching technology, unlike in developed countries as they have ample technological resources to support the large class learning environment (Hornsby & Oman, 2014).

In this regards heavy teaching workload impinge the efforts of quality teacher preparation in sampled universities as one academic staff could handle up to five courses per semester in a large populated class of around 1000 students. Conducting teaching in such situations attribute to poor class management, and low working moral (Exeter et al., 2010; Mulryan-kyne, 2010). Indeed researchers acknowledge that adequate academic staff in the key resource to quality output (Garwe, 2015; Tella & Daniel, 2013) this is to say the achievement of excellent in teaching and learning depend on the calibre of academic staff universities has (Mwebi & Simatwa, 2013; Dill & Soo, 2005; Teferra & Altbach, 2004; Lomas & MacGregor, 2003).

Furthermore, the study also revealed that the use of part-time faculty was yet another indication of shortage of adequate academic staff particularly senior one. All universities under review used part-time academic staff as a result of shortage of academic staff particularly senior academic staff.

The situation here is 50 by 50 (full-time lecturers is 50% and part-time is 50%). In almost all departments dealing with teacher preparation we have neither professors nor senior lecturers. The situation is not promising, so we are working hard to resolve the matter because our focus is on quality teacher preparation (**Interview-Dean; MUM**).

Another respondent added:

The ratio of academic staff in relation to students' ratio is inadequate.....Certainly the uses of part-time lecturers from nearby universities and other from UDSM and UDOM have minimized the shortage of academic staff (**Interview-QAC; MUM**).

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The practice of engaging part-time academic staff was, however conflicting the TCU guideline. During documentary analysis,(TCU, 2014) guideline states that employment of part-time academic staff should be treated as last resort. “Universities should employ sufficient number of staff who should be responsible for the management and delivery of its programme and other activities” (TCU, 2014 p.40). Under this guideline, it was expected that a large number of academic staff would be full-time lecturers. On the other hand, the problem is more acute in private universities than public universities. The finding support previous research that found that over two third of senior academic staff in most of the private universities was part-time (Peter, 2010); Ishengoma, 2007;Ozturgut, 2009). Arguably private universities use part-time lecturers as cost effective measure resolve the shortage of academic staff mainly senior lecturer (Alexander, Maureen, Phillip & Bernadette 2014).

In deed universities to use part-time may probably seem healthy for financial implication of the universities but can be detrimental to the provision of high quality teacher preparation. This is due to the facts that part-timer lecturers spend a greater proportion of their time in teaching from universities to universities but evidence suggests that they are less available to students and rarely available at the campus environment for interaction with students outside the classroom environment, which in turn affect students learning negatively (Jaeger & Hinz, 2009; Kevin, & Jaeger, 2008). Similar findings were observed by Ishengoma (2007), who contended that employment of part-time lecturers implies insecurity of tenure among the academic staff and has negative influenced on the quality of learning.

Contrary to Kevin and Jaeger (2008); Jaeger and Hinz (2009), findings were observed by Wambui, Ngari, and Waititu (2016), in their study on teaching experience of part-time lecturers affect the quality of universities in public universities education in Kenya. They found out that the majority of part-time lecturers have more than five years’ experience in university teaching and they have wide knowledge and skills coverage in their area of specialization; thus enabling them making positive input on leaning process.

However, evidence indicate that universities engage part-time lecturers, particularly senior academic staff (professor and senior lecturers) as a cost cutting measure (Alexander, Maureen, Phillip & Bernadette 2014; Ishengoma, 2007). It is worth to consider how these part-time

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lecturers are supported for effective teaching, research and consultation as their main core function in universities and community at large by providing comfortable offices, and other teaching resources (Nicol & Nicol, 2006) to ensure quality output teachers in particular.

6. Study conclusion and recommendations

Based on the study findings, it is concluded that: All visited universities were found to have inadequate senior academic staffs (professors and senior lecturers) that are keys to knowledge production and teaching conducting edge cutting knowledge. Available senior academic staff engaged with heavy teaching workload in all visited universities in a way it does not encourage them in effective teacher preparation. Secondly, a shortage of senior academic staff especially in private university led to massive engagement of part-time academic staff specifically senior lecturers which are not healthy to quality learning particularly quality teacher preparation. Astonishing the practice of part-time lecturers at universities specifically private universities is out of what is recommended by TCU guideline. Part-time lecturers are often not available for extended period in the host institution and indeed, deprive students of their rightfully consultation hours in the home institutions. Furthermore, on the basis of the current study's findings, one can conclude that teacher preparation at studied universities is at risk due to high student teacher ratio especially at public universities and massive uses of part-time lecturers particularly at private universities. In the light of the preceding study conclusion, it is recommended that there is a need to balance student-teacher ratio at universities, as the high student-teacher ratio affects teaching quality (Hagenauer & Volet, 2014). Similarly, there is a need for universities to observe the TCU QAF guideline in relation to academic staff and part-time lecturers in higher learning. TCU should also enforce their guidelines to be observed and implemented at higher learning institutions. This initiative may help to monitor and promote the area of academic staff and its practice at universities and raise awareness regarding quality teachers' preparation. Again, future research could also be examined particularly to find the status of academic staff qualification and its implications on the graduate teacher preparation in Tanzania by using quantitative research approach. Finally, future research could also examine how the process of teacher preparation is being facilitated in overcrowded classrooms.

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